

was applied at 25-30, 45-55, and 70-75 d after seeding (DS).

We monitored BPH and populations of pests such as seed shrimp *Chrissia* sp. and *Cypris* sp., leaf miner *Hydrellia griseola* Fallen, armyworms *Mythimna separata* Walker and *Spodoptera exempta* Walker, and leafroller *Marasmia exigua*. At early rice growth, furadan 10G, fenitrothion

50% EC, and parathion 50% EC were applied at -2, +10-15, and +30-45 DS to control seed shrimp, leaf miner, and armyworm. BPMC 50% EC and fenitrothion/parathion were applied at 25-d intervals 45 DS to control BPH, armyworm, and leafroller. With regular insecticide application, BG379-5 maintained high BPH resistance until Apr 1984,

after which it was heavily attacked by BPH, which occasionally caused hopperburn. In Jun 1984, 60% hopperburn was observed (see table).

Gradually reduced resistance has been typical of several resistant varieties during the last 10 yr. Leafroller and armyworm have occasionally reduced yields, but not seriously. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DEEP WATER

Effect of fertilizers on yield and yield components of medium deep water rice culture in northern Nigeria

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We evaluated the effect of NPK on yield and yield components of a new deep water rice, BKN6986-38-1, at the RRS, Birnin Kebbi, in 1983. BKN6986-38-1 matures 3-4 wk earlier and has 34% higher average yield and better grain appearance than deep water variety FARO 14.

Treatments were 0, 35, or 70 kg/ha each of N, P, and K in 3³ factorial arrangement in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Rice was planted in 3- × 5-m plots on an annually flooded clay soil that had been planted to rice for several years.

One-half N and all P and K were incorporated in wet soil with a hoe, 1 d before transplanting. The remaining N was drilled between rows 21 d after transplanting. NPK sources were ammonium sulfate, single superphosphate, and potassium chloride.

Three-week-old BKN6986-38-1 seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 30-cm spacing at 1 seedling/hill on 12 Aug, which was a late planting. Seedlings were irrigated and supplemental irrigation was applied as needed. The plots were flooded the 3d wk of Sep reaching a depth of 33 cm. The floodwater receded 1 mo later. The crop matured 15 Nov.

There was a highly significant yield

Effect of NPK fertilizers on grain yield and yield components of deep water rice BKN6986-38-1, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria, 1983.

Fertilizer dose (kg/ha) N - P - K	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Field grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)
0 - 0 - 0	1.7	133	107	28
0 - 0 - 35	1.3	75	97	27
0 - 0 - 70	2.1	138	90	26
0 - 35 - 0	2.3	149	124	29
0 - 35 - 35	3.0	173	112	29
0 - 35 - 70	1.7	115	112	28
0 - 70 - 0	2.1	133	122	27
0 - 70 - 35	2.5	122	108	27
0 - 70 - 70	1.8	122	101	26
35 - 0 - 0	3.0	153	99	28
35 - 0 - 35	2.6	171	109	30
35 - 0 - 70	2.4	151	106	26
35 - 35 - 0	2.8	164	82	28
35 - 35 - 35	3.7	175	109	28
35 - 35 - 70	2.9	155	102	28
35 - 70 - 0	3.3	169	132	29
35 - 70 - 35	2.8	167	101	30
35 - 70 - 70	2.7	164	126	29
70 - 0 - 0	3.5	209	100	27
70 - 0 - 35	3.4	215	119	29
70 - 0 - 70	3.1	191	106	30
70 - 35 - 0	3.7	189	119	28
70 - 35 - 35	3.7	217	109	30
70 - 35 - 70	3.5	191	111	29
70 - 70 - 0	3.3	186	112	29
70 - 70 - 35	3.3	218	113	30
70 - 70 - 70	3.3	186	129	30

LSD for N** at 5%	0.3 t/ha	13.2/m ²	NS N** (at 5% 0.6 g	
1%	0.4 t/ha	17.6/m ²	K** (at 1% 0.8 g	
LSD for P* at 5%	0.3 t/ha		NP** (at 5% 1.02 g	
			NK** (at 1% 1.40 g	
Coefficient of variability	23.7%	17.1%	20.8%	4.4%

*Means significantly differ at 5% level. **Means significantly differ at 1% level. NS Means are not significantly different.

increase with 35 kg N/ha and a further significant increase with 70 kg N/ha (see table). Grain yield significantly increased with 35 kg P/ha, but had no response to higher application. K at 35 kg/ha did not influence yield. At higher doses, it decreased yield but improved 1,000-grain

weight. The interactions N × P, N × K, and N × P × K did not significantly affect grain yield.

There was a linear increase in panicles/m² with N application, but the number of filled grains was not significantly affected. □